

PRACTICAL RESULTS AND PROSPECTS FOR EXPANDING YOUTH PARTICIPATION IN THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPING THE ECONOMY OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: Youth participation plays a pivotal role in shaping the economy of New Uzbekistan. With nearly half of the country's population being young, initiatives to engage and educate this demographic are critical to fostering innovation, sustainable growth, and long-term development. Over the past decade, Uzbekistan has achieved remarkable progress in youth education and skill development, reflecting broader economic transformation and modernization. This article highlights key developments in education, literacy, and youth participation while exploring prospects for future economic engagement.

Key words: society, youth, economic, population, education, policy, business, strategy.

Introduction

Raising a healthy and harmonious generation, turning them into active and direct participants in the political, social and economic reforms being implemented in the country, a real pillar and support of society, remains one of the priority and strategic tasks of our country. In particular, over the past 7 years, a total of about 100 laws and by-laws have been adopted on the effectiveness of youth policy, including the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy" on September 14, 2016. On June 30, 2017, the Youth Union of Uzbekistan was established, the main goal of which was to support and implement all initiatives of young people. By the Law "On Establishing Youth Day in the Republic of Uzbekistan", June 30 was declared "Youth Day". [4]

At the initiative of our President, 2024 was declared the "Year of Youth and Business Support" in our country, and a decree was issued on the work to be carried out in all spheres of our country's social life this year.[3] It is no exaggeration to say that this was a recognition of the vital role and place of the youth of our country in implementing such goals as the prosperity and rise of our country, the well-being and dignity of its citizens, and the inclusion of our country among the advanced societies in the world.

Nowadays, in the process of building the New Uzbekistan Strategy, increasing the participation of students and youth in social processes is of great importance, because students and youth are the country's socio-political strategic subject. Students and youth are the only force that drives the New Uzbekistan Strategy.

Because it is the youth that acts as a bridge between the modern stage of the social system.

Currently, according to the population of Uzbekistan as of October 1, 2024, the country's population is 37,355,356 people. These figures indicate that students and young people are the basis for both quantitative and qualitative changes in the infrastructure of the promising development of society, the development of promising social processes. Because the social characteristics inherent in young people - their worldview, level of knowledge, spirituality, and human qualities - undoubtedly have an impact on the general level and development of society.

The main part

In our country, measures are being taken to form well-rounded students, raise them to be spiritually, morally and physically healthy, and turn them into active strategic participants in the ongoing socio-political reforms. In order to form the knowledge and skills of schoolchildren, educate them in the spirit of loyalty to national and universal values, increase the prestige of the teaching profession and the quality of educators, improve textbooks and educational and methodological complexes in accordance with the requirements of the time, and create modern models of public education institutions that meet international standards, as well as in accordance with the state program for the implementation of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the "Year of Human Dignity and Active Neighborhood", the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-134 dated May 11, 2022 "On Approval of the National Program for the Development of Public Education in 2022-2026" was adopted. This Decree approved the National Program for the Development of Public Education in 2022-2026. The development program identifies priority areas such as the systematic organization of spiritual and educational work in general secondary educational institutions, the establishment of continuous monitoring, evaluation and forecasting mechanisms in this area, increasing the role of the family, especially parents, in the education of children, the meaningful organization of students' free time, improving the system of directing them to professions, as well as strengthening the integration of children with special educational needs into the public education system and accelerating inclusive education processes.

In conclusion, it should be said that the Development Program aims to increase the participation of students in social processes, further strengthen their responsibility to the state, work with gifted students in secondary education institutions, improve the system of meaningful organization of students' free time and their orientation to the profession, introduce a system of support for creative and gifted students, create a single electronic platform for identifying the interests and abilities of students, and introduce an electronic "Workbook" for each student in grades 5-11, as well as introduce scientific and practical programs such as improving the education system and expanding inclusive education processes for children with special educational needs. The development program serves as a system that creates a foundation for young people to develop spiritual and intellectual potential, a strong

belief in their bright future, a professional career, and a mature workforce that meets the requirements of international standards. In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-269 dated December 21, 2022 “On measures to implement administrative reforms in New Uzbekistan” was adopted. It is worth noting that the Ministry of Preschool and School Education was established based on this Decree.

Table 1

Year	Preschool Educational Organizations	General Education Institutions	Students in General Education Institutions	Students in Academic Lyceums	Students in Colleges	Literacy Rate of Young People (16-24)
2019	6,968	10,090	6,168,198	43,193	239,239	100.0
2020	7,753	10,181	6,287,885	40,909	56,959	100.0
2021	7,868	10,289	6,304,586	35,873	95,216	100.0
2022	8,412	10,522	6,461,741	32,418	95,144	100.0
2023	35,973	10,750	6,645,119	32,559	60,327	100.0

From **Table 1** above, we can conclude the following: [5]

The foundation of youth empowerment lies in access to quality education. Over the years, Uzbekistan has undertaken significant reforms in its education sector. The number of preschool educational organizations increased dramatically, rising from 6,968 in 2019 to 35,973 in 2023. This expansion reflects a strong governmental focus on early childhood education, ensuring that the youngest members of society begin their educational journeys with a solid foundation. Similarly, the number of general education institutions grew steadily, from 10,090 in 2019 to 10,750 in 2023. These schools are crucial for equipping young people with foundational knowledge and skills.

The number of students in general education institutions rose consistently, from 6.16 million in 2019 to 6.64 million in 2023. This growth indicates improved access to education and reflects demographic trends and policy reforms aimed at mandatory school attendance.

Despite successes in primary education, enrollment in academic lyceums and colleges has seen fluctuations. The number of students in lyceums declined from 43,193 in 2019 to 32,559 in 2023. Similarly, college enrollment dropped sharply from 239,239 in 2019 to 60,327 in 2023. These trends may signal a shift in focus toward vocational and higher education opportunities.

Uzbekistan boasts a **100% literacy rate among young people aged 16-24** from 2019 to 2023. This achievement underscores the country’s commitment to universal education and positions its youth as a literate, capable workforce ready to engage in economic activities. However, ensuring literacy translates into employable skills remains a critical challenge for policymakers.

Conclusion

The youth of Uzbekistan represent a powerful driving force for the nation's economic growth and transformation. Their creativity, energy, and ability to adapt to emerging trends position them as key contributors to the development of a knowledge-based, innovative, and sustainable economy. The progress in education reforms and the strong literacy rate among young people underscore their readiness to participate actively in the economic sphere.

Youth-driven initiatives such as entrepreneurship, mobility, and green economy projects are beginning to reshape key sectors, creating jobs and introducing modern practices that enhance productivity and competitiveness. The steady rise in general education enrollment and the government's investments in youth-focused programs are creating a well-prepared, capable workforce. This workforce is not only addressing traditional economic demands but is also pushing the boundaries in new industries like technology, digital marketing, and renewable energy.

By strategically integrating youth into all aspects of the economy—through policy development, business support, and education—the government ensures that their potential is fully utilized. In doing so, Uzbekistan is empowering its young population to lead the nation toward sustainable economic prosperity. The future of Uzbekistan's economy is inherently tied to its youth, making their development and participation not just a priority but a necessity for achieving the ambitious goals of the New Uzbekistan Strategy.

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